

1 **Supporting information**

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3 ***Longitudinal Eosinophil-derived neurotoxin measurements and asthma***

4 ***development in preschool wheezers***

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20 **Asthma definition**

21 The definition of asthma at age 7 was based on the Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) guidelines
22 (ASTHMA, 2021) and included one mandatory criterion (a diagnosis of asthma by the study doctor, a
23 pediatric allergist) and three additional optional criteria: lower respiratory symptoms, medication for
24 treatment of wheeze the preceding 12 months or airway reversibility >12% after the use of
25 bronchodilator with salbutamol, as previously described (HOLMDAHL; FILIOU; STENBERG HAMMAR;
26 ASARNOJ *et al.*, 2021). Lower respiratory symptoms were defined as cough, shortness of breath and
27 nocturnal awakening caused by wheezing for 5 days or longer the preceding 12 months. All children
28 that fulfilled the mandatory and at least one of the optional criteria (symptoms, medication or
29 reversibility) were classified as having asthma.

30

31 **Study design and cohort data**

32 The “Gene Expression in Wheezing and Asthmatic Children” (GEWAC) is a longitudinal cohort
33 consisting of 156 cases and 102 age-matched healthy controls, as previously described (STENBERG
34 HAMMAR; HEDLIN; KONRADSEN; NORDLUND *et al.*, 2014). Cases (≥ 6 months to ≤ 3 years) were
35 enrolled at the pediatric emergency ward at Astrid Lindgren’s Children’s Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden,
36 between 2008 and 2012 when visiting with acute wheeze. The cases came to a first revisit three
37 months later, followed prospectively until age seven. Age-matched controls were recruited during the
38 same time. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are given in **Table S1**.

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40 **Table S1:** Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study cohort

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	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Cases N=156	-Age of 6 to 48 months -Acute symptoms of wheeze	-Prematurity (birth before 36 gestational weeks) -Chronic disease -Simultaneous complications (e.g., sepsis, bacterial pneumonia)
Controls N=102	-Age of 6 to 48 months	-Prematurity (birth before 36 gestational weeks) -History of bronchial obstruction and asthma or known sensitization to airborne allergens.

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43 The children are well characterized with clinical examinations by the study doctor, standardized
44 questionnaires, and biological sampling at all visits. Included in this study are longitudinal EDN
45 measurements and clinical information from the cases at acute visit (n=81), the first revisit after 3
46 months (n=103), and the visits at age 4 (n=59) and at age 7 (n=84), and for the controls at inclusion

47 (n=43) and at age 7 (n=27), depending on availability of serum. The information on the age of cases
 48 and controls is shown in **Table S2**.

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50 **Table S2:** Age (in months) distribution of the study cohort.

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		Case	Controls	<i>p-value</i>	Case		<i>p-value</i>
					Asthma	Non-Asthma	
Age In months Median (IQR)	Inclusion	22.00 (15.75-28.25) [N = 80]	18.00 (12.50-28.00) [N = 43]	0.290	23.00 (18.75-31.00) [N = 36]	19.00 (13.75-23.50) [N = 24]	0.037
	Revisit at 3 months	22.00 (16.00-29.00) [N = 103]	-	-	23.00 (16.00-31.00) [N = 57]	19.00 (17.00-26.00) [N = 25]	0.483
	Annual visit at age of 4 y	48.00 (45.00-51.00) [N = 58]	-	-	48.00 (45.00-51.00) [N = 37]	48.50 (45.25-50.75) [N = 14]	0.791
	Annual visit at age of 7 y	84.00 (83.00-86.00) [N = 69]	83.00 (82.75-85.25) [N = 24]	0.210	84.00 (83.00-85.00) [N = 49]	84.00 (83.00-86.00) [N = 20]	0.401

52 *Median values, interquartile range (IQR) and sample numbers [N] are given in the table. Case= Preschool wheezers,*
 53 *Control = healthy controls, Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age, Non-*
 54 *Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that do not have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age. The statistical comparison*
 55 *performed by two-tailed Mann–Whitney U test.*

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57 A self-reported asthma control test (ACT) (LIU; ZEIGER; SORKNESS; MAHR *et al.*, 2007; NATHAN;
 58 SORKNESS; KOSINSKI; SCHATZ *et al.*, 2004) and lung function (FEV%) (MILLER; HANKINSON; BRUSASCO;
 59 BURGOS *et al.*, 2005) at the visit at age 7 was assessed. At age 7, children (cases and controls) were
 60 assessed regarding asthma diagnosis.

61

62 *A standardized questionnaire* regarding ethnicity, lifestyle, family history of asthma and allergies,
 63 *breastfeeding, exposure to tobacco smoke, pets and previous infections, the occurrence of atopic and*
 64 *asthmatic symptoms, and use of asthma medication was filled out at the first revisit. Another*
 65 *standardized questionnaire regarding atopic symptoms as well as occurrence, frequency, and duration*
 66 *of asthmatic symptoms and use of asthma medication during the preceding 12 months was filled out*
 67 *at each annual follow-up. Associations between asthma at age 7 and parental asthma, daycare, and*
 68 *medication are shown in **Table S3 and S4**.*

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74 **Table S3:** Proportion of acute wheeze in cases with an asthma diagnosis at age 7 (asthma)
 75 and cases that do not have an asthma diagnosis at age 7 (non-asthma) in children with a
 76 history of parental asthma and daycare.
 77

		Parental asthma	<i>p-value</i>	Daycare/preschool	<i>p-value</i>
Inclusion	Non-asthma (22)	5 (22.73%)	0.381	19 (86.36%)	0.667
	Asthma (35)	13 (37.14%)		32 (91.42%)	
Revisit at 3 months	Non-asthma (25)	5 (20.00%)	0.083	21 (84.00%)	0.566
	Asthma (57)	9 (40.35%)		44 (77.19%)	
Annual visit at the age of 4y	Non-asthma (14)	2 (14.29%)	0.300	8 (57.14%)	0.746
	Asthma (38)	13 (34.21%)		25 (65.79%)	
Annual visit at the age of 7y	Non-asthma (23)	7 (30.43%)	0.798	17 (73.91%)	1.000
	Asthma (60)	22 (36.67%)		45 (75.00%)	

78 *Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age, Non-Asthma = preschool*
 79 *wheezers (cases) that do not have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age. P-values were calculated by Fisher's*
 80 *Exact Test.*
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83 **Table S4:** Proportion of acute wheeze (asthma, non-asthma) children with (yes) or without
 84 (no) LTRA and ICS medication within 24 hours of visit.
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	LTRA	Asthma	P-value	ICS	Asthma	P-value
Inclusion	No (50)	28 (56.00%)	0.289	No (32)	18 (56.25%)	0.603
	Yes (10)	8 (80.00%)		Yes (28)	18 (64.29%)	
Revisit at 3 months	No (68)	47 (69.12%)	1.000	No (18)	12 (66.67%)	0.778
	Yes (14)	10 (71.43%)		Yes (64)	45 (70.31%)	
Annual visit at age of 4	No (45)	32 (71.11%)	0.659	No (34)	23 (67.65%)	0.329
	Yes (7)	6 (85.71%)		Yes (18)	15 (83.33%)	
Annual visit at age of 7	No (82)	58 (70.73%)	1.000	No (76)	52 (68.42%)	0.098
	Yes (2)	2 (100.00%)		Yes (8)	8 (100.00%)	

86 *Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age, Non-Asthma = preschool*
 87 *wheezers (cases) that do not have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age. P-values are calculated by Fisher's Exact*
 88 *Test.*
 89

90 Blood samples were collected at each visit and analyzed at the laboratories of Clinical Chemistry, and
91 of Clinical Immunology, Karolinska University Hospital, Stockholm Sweden. Blood samples were
92 collected at each visit and analyzed for complete blood count (**Figure S1, Table S5**). Allergen-specific
93 IgE antibodies against a mix of common food allergens, fx5, (milk, egg white, wheat, codfish, peanut
94 and soya bean), and a mix of common airborne allergens, Phadiatop, (house dust mite, cat, horse, dog,
95 timothy, birch and mugwort, *Cladosporium herbarum*), were analyzed using the ImmunoCAP System
96 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Uppsala, Sweden) at inclusion, 3-month revisit and at age 7 (**Table S6**).
97 Allergic sensitization was defined as allergen-specific IgE ≥ 0.35 kUA/L.

98
99 **Figure S1:** Modelling of longitudinal trajectories for (A) leukocytes, (B) neutrophils, (C) lymphocytes,
100 and (D) monocytes.

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Table S5: Different blood cell counts in the study cohort.

		Case	Control	<i>p-value</i>	Cases		<i>p-value</i>
					Asthma	Non-Asthma	
leukocytes N×10 ⁹ /L (IQR)	Inclusion	11.10 (8.90-13.75) [N = 79]	8.35 (6.38- 10.58) [N = 40]	9.2×10 ⁻³	11.20 (9.25-13.40) [N = 35]	11.10 (9.20-14.45) [N = 23]	0.918
	Revisit at 3 months	9.10 (7.40-11.10) [N = 99]	-	-	8.80 (7.10-10.80) [N = 57]	9.25 (8.25-11.45) [N = 22]	0.317
	Annual visit at age of 4y	7.70 (6.43-9.00) [N = 54]	-	-	7.60 (6.25-8.30) [N = 35]	7.90 (6.75-9.75) [N = 14]	0.352
	Annual visit at age of 7y	7.05 (5.88-8.60) [N = 80]	7.10 (5.78-8.43) [N = 24]	0.926	7.10 (5.73-9.05) [N = 56]	7.00 (6.08-8.08) [N = 24]	0.694
neutrophils N×10 ⁹ /L (IQR)	Inclusion	7.40 (4.75-10.35) [N = 79]	2.60 (1.90-3.43) [N = 40]	1.3×10 ⁻¹²	7.50 (5.75-9.60) [N = 35]	6.60 (4.10-9.10) [N = 23]	0.357
	Revisit at 3 months	3.20 (2.20-4.25) [N = 99]	-	-	3.00 (2.00-4.20) [N = 57]	3.40 (2.40-3.78) [N = 22]	0.690
	Annual visit at age of 4y	3.05 (2.63-4.00) [N = 54]	-	-	2.90 (2.55-4.00) [N = 35]	3.45 (3.13-3.98) [N = 14]	0.287
	Annual visit at age of 7y	3.20 (2.38-4.40) [N = 80]	3.30 (2.50-4.20) [N = 24]	0.841	3.05 (2.30-4.60) [N = 56]	3.40 (2.58-4.33) [N = 24]	1.000
lymphocytes N×10 ⁹ /L (IQR)	Inclusion	2.50 (1.60-3.60) [N = 79]	4.55 (3.20-5.78) [N = 40]	1.2×10 ⁻⁷	2.60 (1.50-3.65) [N = 35]	2.90 (2.15-3.95) [N = 23]	0.246
	Revisit at 3 months	4.70 (3.90-5.70) [N = 99]	-	-	4.50 (3.80-5.60) [N = 57]	5.15 (4.10-6.08) [N = 22]	0.186
	Annual visit at age of 4y	3.50 (2.83-3.90) [N = 54]	-	-	3.30 (2.85-3.90) [N = 35]	3.40 (2.73-4.35) [N = 14]	0.756
	Annual visit at age of 7y	2.75 (2.30-3.30) [N = 80]	2.90 (2.48-3.33) [N = 24]	0.532	2.80 (2.38-3.23) [N = 56]	2.70 (2.20-3.50) [N = 24]	0.793
monocytes N×10 ⁹ /L (IQR)	Inclusion	0.90 (0.60-1.30) [N = 79]	0.65 (0.50-0.93) [N = 40]	0.030	0.90 (0.65-1.30) [N = 35]	1.00 (0.50-1.60) [N = 23]	0.750
	Revisit at 3 months	0.70 (0.60-0.90) [N = 99]	-	-	0.70 (0.60-0.80) [N = 57]	0.75 (0.60-1.00) [N = 22]	0.281
	Annual visit at age of 4y	0.60 (0.50-0.70) [N = 54]	-	-	0.50 (0.50-0.70) [N = 35]	0.70 (0.60-0.70) [N = 14]	0.103
	Annual visit at age of 7y	0.50 (0.40-0.70) [N = 80]	0.50 (0.40-0.60) [N = 24]	0.257	0.50 (0.40-0.70) [N = 56]	0.50 (0.40-0.70) [N = 24]	0.949

104 *Median values, interquartile range (IQR) and sample numbers [N] are given in the table. Case= Preschool wheezers,*
 105 *Control = healthy controls, Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age, Non-*
 106 *Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that do not have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age. The statistical comparison*
 107 *performed by two-tailed Mann–Whitney U test.*

108 **Table S6:** Proportion of acute wheeze in cases that have an asthma diagnosis at age 7 (asthma) and
 109 cases that do not have an asthma diagnosis at age 7 (non-asthma) children with positive fx5 and
 110 phadiatop tests. P-values were calculated by Fisher's Exact Test.
 111

		Positive fx5	p-value	Positive phadiatop	p-value
Inclusion	Non-asthma (16)	3 (18.75%)	0.715	0 (0.00%)	0.033
	Asthma (26)	7 (26.92%)		7 (26.92%)	
Revisit at 3 months	Non-asthma (20)	5 (25.00%)	1.000	1 (5.00%)	0.249
	Asthma (40)	9 (22.50%)		7 (17.50%)	
Annual visit at the age of 7y	Non-asthma (23)	2 (8.70%)	0.080	3 (13.04%)	0.058
	Asthma (58)	16 (27.59%)		21 (36.21%)	

112 *Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age, Non-Asthma = preschool*
 113 *wheezers (cases) that do not have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age*

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115 Analysis of serum EDN was performed using a custom-made chip-based microarray research assay
 116 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Uppsala, Sweden). Briefly, a pair of complementary monoclonal antibodies
 117 (mAbs) was used where the capture mAb was printed to reaction wells on a Maxisorp slide (Fisher
 118 Scientific) using an Aushon printer and the detection mAb was labelled with fluorescence DyLight 550
 119 (Microscale Antibody Labeling Kit, ThermoScientific). The reaction wells on the slides were incubated
 120 with 30µl of serum samples diluted 1:30. The sample and fluorescence conjugate incubation times
 121 were 2 hours and 30 minutes, respectively. The incubations were performed at room temperature in
 122 a humidity chamber and were terminated by extensive washing steps using ImmunoCAP Washing
 123 Solution. The fluorescence detection conjugate was used to measure bound EDN, and the fluorescence
 124 intensity was measured by a Tecan LS Reloaded laser scanner to obtain fluorescent intensities reported
 125 as arbitrary units (AU). The generated fluorescence was proportional to the formed EDN-antibody
 126 complexes. Relation between blood eosinophil (B-Eos) counts and EDN levels is shown in **Figure S2**.

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128 Associations of allergic sensitization and medication to EDN levels, and B-Eos count are shown in
 129 **Table S7, S8** and **Figure S3, S4** respectively. The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves of
 130 asthma prediction by EDN levels and blood eosinophil counts are shown in **Figure S5**.

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Figure S2: Correlation between blood eosinophil counts and EDN levels.

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Table S7: EDN levels with allergic sensitization.

	EDN levels (AU)		Log ₁₀ transformed EDN-levels		p-value
	Positive fx5	Negative fx5	Positive fx5	Negative fx5	
Inclusion	3027.8 (1500.3-4620.6) [N = 19]	1829 (1414-3077) [N = 55]	3.481 (3.175-3.664) [N = 19]	3.262 (3.150-3.488) [N = 55]	0.256
Revisit at 3 months	3194.9 (2325.8-8242.5) [N = 19]	3531.8 (2220.7-5914.9) [N = 59]	3.504 (3.366-3.916) [N = 19]	3.548 (3.346-3.772) [N = 59]	0.945
Annual visit at age of 7	4836 (3423-7536) [N = 23]	3538.2 (2221.0-6044.1) [N = 83]	3.684 (3.534-3.877) [N = 23]	3.549 (3.347-3.781) [N = 83]	0.066

	EDN levels (AU)		Log ₁₀ transformed EDN levels		p-value
	Positive phadiatop	Negative phadiatop	Positive phadiatop	Negative phadiatop	
Inclusion	2941 (1789- 4383) [N = 9]	1858 (1303-3269) [N = 65]	3.468 (3.253-3.642) [N = 9]	3.269 (3.115-3.514) [N = 65]	0.090
Revisit at 3 months	4965 (3713-6907) [N = 9]	3465.8 (2035.2-5791.9) [N = 69]	3.696 (3.570-3.839) [N = 9]	3.540 (3.309-3.763) [N = 69]	0.063
Annual visit at age of 7y	6044 (3642-8641) [N = 27]	3525.8 (2221.0-5248.6) [N = 79]	3.781 (3.560-3.937) [N = 27]	3.547 (3.347-3.720) [N = 79]	0.001

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Median values, interquartile range (IQR), and sample numbers [N] are given in the table. AU = arbitrary fluorescent units. The statistical comparison was performed by t-test.

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Table S8: Blood eosinophil count in relation to allergic sensitization.

		Positive fx5	Negative fx5	<i>p</i> -value	Positive phadiatop	Negative phadiatop	<i>p</i> -value
Blood eosinophil (N×10 ⁹ /L)	Inclusion	0.200 (0.200-0.450) [N = 7]	0.200 (0.125-0.300) [N = 22]	0.674	0.200 (0.200-0.250) [N = 3]	0.200 (0.125-0.450) [N = 26]	1.000
	Revisit at 3 months	0.500 (0.200-0.600) [N = 17]	0.300 (0.200-0.600) [N = 52]	0.844	0.500 (0.300-0.700) [N = 9]	0.300 (0.200-0.600) [N = 60]	0.253
	Annual visit at age of 7y	0.500 (0.275-0.650) [N = 20]	0.300 (0.200-0.600) [N = 73]	0.141	0.500 (0.225-0.775) [N = 26]	0.300 (0.200-0.500) [N = 67]	0.027

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Median values, interquartile range (IQR) and sample numbers [N] are given in the table. The statistical comparison performed by two-tailed Mann–Whitney U test.

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Figure S3: Longitudinal blood eosinophil counts in preschool wheezers that had medication with (color: red) or without (color: green) LTRA (A) and ICS (B) within the last 24 hours of visit. (C) and (D) show modeling of longitudinal trajectories of blood eosinophil counts. LTRA = leukotriene receptor antagonist, ICS = inhaled corticosteroids.

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153 **Figure S4:** Longitudinal EDN levels in preschool wheezers that had medication with (color: red) or
 154 without (color: green) LTRA (A) and ICS (B) within the last 24 hours of visit. (C) and (D) show modeling
 155 of longitudinal trajectories of EDN expression. LTRA = leukotriene receptor antagonist, ICS = inhaled
 156 corticosteroids.

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 161 **Figure S5:** ROC curves of asthma prediction by EDN levels and blood eosinophil counts at (A) inclusion,
 162 (B) revisit at follow-up in 3 months, (C) annual visit at age 4, and (D) age 7.

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 164 Nasopharyngeal swabs for viral detection were sampled at the emergency visit and analyzed as
 165 previously described (STENBERG HAMMAR; HEDLIN; KONRADSEN; NORDLUND *et al.*, 2014). Vitamin D
 166 levels (25(OH)D) were assessed using direct, competitive chemiluminescence analysis (CLIA;
 167 DiaSorinInc, Stillwater, MN, USA) as previously described (STENBERG HAMMAR; HEDLIN; KONRADSEN;
 168 NORDLUND *et al.*, 2014).

169
 170 *Spirometry and airway reversibility* were performed using the Medikro Pro spirometer at the 7 years'
 171 follow-up. Reversibility was evaluated 15 minutes after inhalation with 400 micrograms salbutamol
 172 using a spacer. The patient's technique and quality of the spirometry were evaluated according to
 173 international guidelines (MILLER; HANKINSON; BRUSASCO; BURGOS *et al.*, 2005). If the test-criteria
 174 were not fulfilled, the test result was not included in the analyses. The legal guardians were advised

175 not to give their children asthma medication (salbutamol, corticosteroids or leukotriene antagonists)
176 up to 24 hours before the revisit at 7 years of age.

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178 The baseline clinical characteristics of participants are shown in **Table S9**.

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181 **Statistical analyses**

182 We used the Shapiro-Wilk normality test to analyze the normality of different variables in this study.

183 Only the \log_{10} transformed EDN levels followed a normal distribution. Thus, we applied the t-test to

184 measure the significance of the central tendency (*e.g.*, median) of \log_{10} EDN between different groups.

185 Other parameters (age, weight, different blood counts, asthma-related clinical parameters, etc.) were

186 analyzed as raw values. Due to their non-normal distribution, we used non-parametric tests (*e.g.*,

187 Mann-Whitney *U* test, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient). For longitudinal analysis, we used

188 linear mixed models to estimate the temporal profile of that variable. All statistical analyses were

189 performed in R (<https://www.r-project.org/>).

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192 **Table S9: Baseline characteristics of participants in the cohort where EDN levels (AU) are available**
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	Case	Control	p-value	Case		p-value
				Asthma	Non-Asthma	
Inclusion						
Age in months, median (IQR)	22.00 (15.75-28.25) [N = 80]	18.00 (12.50-28.00) [N = 43]	0.290	23.00 (18.75-31.00) [N = 36]	19.00 (13.75-23.50) [N = 24]	0.037
Male sex, N (%)	53 (65.43)	37 (86.05)	0.019	24 (66.67)	16 (66.67)	1.000
Caucasian mother and/or father, N (%)	64 (86.49)	27 (71.05)	0.072	29 (86.36)	19 (82.86)	1.000
Maternal smoking during pregnancy, N (%)	10 (13.51)	2 (4.88)	0.208	5 (14.29)	1 (4.55)	0.389
Exclusive breastfeeding 4 months, N (%)	42 (60.00)	28 (68.29)	0.421	18 (58.06)	15 (68.18)	0.569
Parental asthma/eczema, N (%)	33 (45.83)	9 (22.50)	0.016	19 (57.58)	8 (36.36)	0.171
Previous RSV infection, N (%)	17 (23.61)	1 (2.44)	0.003	9 (27.27)	4 (18.18)	0.528
RV at the emergency visit, N (%)	44 (72.13)			21 (75.00)	12 (66.67)	0.738
Attend preschool or daycare, N (%)	62 (83.78)			30 (85.71)	18 (81.82)	0.722
Reported food allergy at inclusion, N (%)	9 (12.33)	0 (0.00)	0.025	5 (14.71)	1 (4.55)	0.386
fx5 positive, N (%)	15 (27.78)	4 (20.00)	0.565	7 (26.92)	3 (18.75)	0.715
Phadiatop positive, N (%)	8 (14.81)	1 (5.00)	0.429	7 (26.92)	0 (0.00)	0.033
Eczema at inclusion, N (%)	17 (23.61)	2 (4.88)	0.010	10 (30.30)	4 (18.18)	0.361
Vitamin D nmol/L, median (IQR)	79.00 (67.00-95.00) [N = 65]	87.00 (71.00-100.00) [N = 41]	0.252	74.00 (66.00-88.50) [N = 31]	88.00 (72.00-103.00) [N = 19]	0.087
First time wheeze, N (%)	13 (18.31)			4 (12.50)	4 (19.05)	0.698
Hospitalised at inclusion, N (%)	59 (83.10)			26 (81.25)	18 (85.71)	1.000
RTIs at inclusion, N (%)	59 (83.10)			26 (81.25)	18 (85.71)	0.675
Eosinophils at inclusion, median (IQR)	0.20 (0.20-0.50) [N = 17]	0.20 (0.10-0.30) [N = 36]	0.508	0.40 (0.23-0.58) [N = 6]	0.20 (0.10-0.20) [N = 9]	0.067
Neutrophils at inclusion, median (IQR)	7.40 (4.75-10.35) [N = 79]	2.60 (1.90-3.43) [N = 40]	1.3×10^{-12}	7.50 (5.75-9.60) [N = 35]	6.60 (4.10-9.10) [N = 23]	0.357
Annual visit at age of 7 years						
Age in months, median (IQR)	84.00 (83.00-86.00) [N = 69]	83.00 (82.75-85.25) [N = 24]	0.210	84.00 (83.00-85.00) [N = 49]	84.00 (83.00-86.00) [N = 20]	0.401
fx5 positive, N (%)	18 (22.22)	5 (20.0)	1.000	16 (27.59)	2 (8.70)	0.080
Phadiatop positive, N (%)	24 (29.63)	3 (12.00)	0.114	21 (36.21)	3 (13.04)	0.058
Eosinophils, median (IQR)	0.40 (0.20-0.60) [N = 75]	0.30 (0.20-0.40) [N = 21]	0.103	0.40 (0.20-0.73) [N = 52]	0.30 (0.20-0.45) [N = 23]	0.102
Blood eosinophil (> 0.3 × 10 ⁹ /L)	38 (50.00%)	6 (28.57%)	0.090	30 (56.60%)	8 (34.78%)	0.133
Neutrophils, median (IQR)	3.20 (2.38-4.40) [N = 80]	3.30 (2.50-4.20) [N = 24]	0.841	3.05 (2.30-4.60) [N = 56]	3.40 (2.58-4.33) [N = 24]	1.000
FeNO, median (IQR)	9.50 (6.75-14.00) [N = 32]	8.00 (5.75-10.25) [N = 12]	0.217	11.50 (6.25-15.75) [N = 22]	7.00 (6.25-8.75) [N = 10]	0.146
FEV%, median (IQR)	88.56 (82.99-93.58) [N = 82]	92.22 (87.03-97.11) [N = 26]	0.068	88.36 (82.99-92.37) [N = 60]	89.59 (83.25-93.84) [N = 24]	0.384
Eczema, N (%)	7 (8.33)	1 (3.85)	0.678	7 (11.67)	0 (0.00)	0.184
Asthma Control Test, median (IQR)	25.00 (22.25-26.00) [N = 74]			24.00 (21.50-26.00) [N = 55]	27.00 (26.00-27.00) [N = 19]	5.0 × 10⁻⁶

194 *Median values were calculated by Mann–Whitney U test, and proportional differences between two groups*
 195 *were calculated by Fisher’s exact test. Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that have an asthma diagnosis at 7*
 196 *years of age, Non-Asthma = preschool wheezers (cases) that do not have an asthma diagnosis at 7 years of age.*

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